

R&D Programs as Instruments for Governmental R&D Funding Policy

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ABSTRACT

Major developments in governmental research and development (R&D) funding are associated with the emergence of programs as funding instruments. Programs include an explicit mission for R&D, scientific priorities including type of research to be undertaken, procedures for attaining funding, and a budget that also contains regulations for monitoring and evaluation.

A better understanding of programs implies understanding how R&D government policies are put into actions by research funding organizations and how funding programs are designed and implemented to address problems of social relevance nominated at policy levels.

The aim of this chapter is to give a broad overview of the main theoretical advancements dealing with programs as instruments of governmental R&D policy. It seeks to explore two questions: what is the role of programs in government funding of R&D? How can we understand programs theoretically and design frameworks to empirically study them?

A first contribution is to illustrate the diversity and the complex nature of research programs, as well as the strategies and objectives they reveal, the actors implementing the programs and the modes of implementation. A second contribution of the chapter is to develop new conceptual framings based on this theoretical review, also indicating relevant methods for doing empirical studies. Examples of recent and currently developing empirical data and infrastructures to investigate the diversity of funding programs using new concepts and empirical insights are discussed.

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1. Introduction

The emergence of competition in funding for research and development (R&D) is based on long-term changes in trajectories and rationales for governmental R&D support. Starting from the 1970s, governmental R&D funding was deeply transformed in European countries, and a project-based mode of allocation became more dominant. This had two main reasons. First, stagnation of the volume of public research funding induced more selective modes of allocation. Second, new policy rationales about efficient use of public resources emphasized competitive allocation as a mean to increase the quality, efficiency, and effectiveness of research systems (Lepori et al., 2007).

The aim of the chapter is to give an overview of the main theoretical advancements dealing with programs as instruments of governmental R&D policy. Programs are meso-level instruments that serve several purposes, such as directing R&D efforts towards specific societal challenges or knowledge domains. They act as coordinating mechanisms, usually for clusters of R&D projects to improve their quality and productivity. Two questions drive our exploration: What is the role of programs in government funding of R&D? How can we understand programs theoretically and devise frameworks for their empirical study? In this context, the chapter illustrates the diversity and the complex nature of research programs, as well as strategies and objectives they reveal, the actors implementing the programs and the modes of implementation. It also develops new conceptual framings based on this theoretical review. Examples of recent and currently developing data and infrastructures to investigate the diversity of funding programs using new concepts and empirical insights are presented.

The chapter primarily focuses on government programs for R&D funding to academic research, mainly performed by universities and non-higher education public research organizations, in some cases in collaboration with the private sector. Such governmental R&D funding may address different topics, and it is possibly oriented at solving societal challenges and needs with varying degree of specific objectives, and rarely oriented at blue skies or curiosity-driven research only. The perimeter also includes investigator-driven grant schemes and not only thematically oriented programs. R&D programs may foresee innovation activities found under labels like pre-competitive research, but this chapter does not discuss instruments per se related to innovation policy devoted to supporting the firms' capabilities to introduce new products in the market and similar.

The chapter is organized as follows. Section 2 presents a fundamental narrative about how programs have emerged and what a governmental R&D funding program is. We discuss different notions of programs in national and supra-national contexts, as well as differences that are linked to sectoral and funding perspectives. By reviewing the literature, Section 3 presents the multifaceted problems of R&D funding programs focusing on the features that are essential to understand them and therefore mobilizing the most important theoretical perspectives to this aim. In addition, it discusses some relevant issues of the current evolution of programs as policy instruments, namely modes of coordination, policy mixes, hybridity of R&D programs, and the portfolio perspective. Moreover, it provides a few examples of research endeavors trying to empirically observe characteristics of R&D funding programs. The chapter ends with a critical assessment of gaps in the theoretical perspectives on research programs and future research directions dealing with open issues (Section 4).

2. R&D funding programs: origins and definition

Defining the peculiar nature of a R&D funding program is difficult. In the context of R&D funding systems, programs have been described as meso level instruments, that distribute project funding (Lepori et al., 2017) to research groups on a regular and systematic basis.

Programs are long-term means of the government to pursue strategic goals such as increasing excellence of the research system or reinforcing the collaboration between public and private research performers. The program design explicates the aim and scope of the actions, the expected results, and the impact foreseen. Also, it indicates the R&D projects funding streams -grants, projects, contracts, funding to networks, that are devoted to put into action the chosen aims and goals. For instance, the Excellence Initiative in Germany is a

large program pursuing the improvement of the quality and international standing of the German universities. The program is articulated into different project funding streams (Graduate schools for early career researchers, Clusters of excellence, Universities of excellence) to the performers on the base of competitive calls. Another example is the FIRST in Italy, a program to sustain the firms' investment on R&D, which is articulated in four project funding lines -international research project funding, social innovation, spin off from research and strategic research projects.

This definition has two main implications. First, programs involve several functions and manage several processes. The main ones are a) the construction of an explicit mission statement, including the goals to be reached; b) the identification of scientific priorities and of the type and mode of research expected; c) procedures and rules for submitting proposals, as well as for their evaluation and selection; and d) a dedicated budget and procedures for contract management, including monitoring and reporting. Programs have different goals, whose attainment might involve different research fields or combinations thereof.

Second, programs can be designed by a research funding organization/agency (RFO) or jointly by two or more funding agencies that mediate between the state and the performing sector. Therefore, programs may vary according to the missions attributed to the funding agencies involved and the policy objectives they must address, and to the policy space of the funding agency following government delegation (Braun, 2006b). Different national contexts have different funding traditions influencing the way in which programs are formulated, the rules and the organizational logics of their management, the fields and beneficiaries addressed, and the regulations affecting the selection and the evaluation processes. In this respect, governmental R&D funding programs differ from targeted funding or project funding since they delineate the content of public policy and the preferences of the actors involved in the design and implementation. Governmental R&D funding programs are clearly visible from the 1970s or in some countries from the 1980s.

During these decades the relationships between science and society, represented through the metaphor of a contract, changed. Before the seventies, the contract foresaw a clear division of tasks between the two parties: government (as representative of the society) supplied money; the scientific community provided knowledge retaining the power to decide the research agenda, methods, and tools to guarantee integrity and social benefits (Guston, 1996). Government maintained the right to decide the level of funding without posing limitations to the autonomy of science (van der Meulen, 1998). Increasingly, this contract came under critique and scrutiny (Weinberg, 1974; Jasanoff, 1987), captured by a new ideal that public funding of research should lead to "socially robust knowledge". This knowledge more explicitly and directly addresses societal needs, seeking to find solutions to emerging problems through the collaborative effort of different actors under a new trans-disciplinary perspective (Gibbons et al., 1994; Martin, 2003). Early efforts and programs often had rather broad goals where the societal need served as an umbrella for regular academic research, thus bringing together related research from different research performing organizations, providing in some cases advantages of additional resources and opportunities for collaboration, with a soft directional steering of research (Mathisen, 1996). At the supranational level, the EU framework programs started in the 1980s fit into this category with their thematic priorities based on negotiations between civil servants and various societal interest groups.

The proliferation of governmental program funding is tied to this fundamental shift in the framing of science policy rationales, moving from a block funding perspective to a goal-oriented one. The emergence of large programs devoted to sustaining research on the frontier of technological innovation (Laredo and Mustar, 2002; Senker, 2006) was one consequence of this new orientation. Another was changing patterns of funding allocation to research performers, emphasizing competitive project-based funding (Lepori et al., 2007; Thèves et al., 2007) that sought higher quality research outputs and positive effects on economic and social growth, by addressing political problems or technological innovation. In this respect, funding became an instrument to steer the research and innovation system, orienting activities and results toward pre-determined goals. Some new funding agencies were established, and many thematically bound programs emerged in funding organizations whose mission was to provide competitive funding for specific scientific disciplines.

National political and economic strategies drove many of the mentioned changes, but a key role was also played by European funding to R&D, mainly through the European Framework Programs, which largely modified both the constellations of actors involved, and the design of the programs (Geuna, 2001; Delanghe et al, 2009). The transformation of the organization of research funding moved from the rationale of complementarity between national R&D funding programs and the European level to a new rationale of competition for funding by launching programs toward the building 'European Science' (Edler et al., 2003; Nedeva and Wedlin, 2015; Braun, 2017; Scherngell and Lata, 2013).

In the new century, further developments at the European policy level pushed for more decisive action toward providing science-based solutions to societal needs. The rhetoric of R&D policy outlined the importance of committed research efforts to find solutions for the so-called Societal Grand Challenges (Kuhlman and Rip, 2018), the importance of research instruments for sustaining the development and the use of Key Enabling Technologies (Martin, 2016), and the strong directionality recommended for research and innovation policy toward the achievement of Sustainable Development Goals (OECD, 2018). New concepts from scholars in the field of science, technology and innovation studies have emerged in parallel with and as a response to the new policy narratives. These include conceptualizations of transformative innovation processes (Schot and Steinmueller, 2018), new attitudes, societal values, and practices in the realm of R&D policy (Kaldewey, 2018) and the need for action aimed at stimulating a more entrepreneurial state driving efforts toward mission-oriented R&D policies (Foray et al., 2011; Mazzucato, 2018). All the mentioned developments have major implications for both the organization and scope of R&D governmental programs. For example, instances of inter-disciplinarity as well as public and private collaboration have been put forward as means to translate research efforts into concrete solutions for the economy and society.

The main argument of this section is that the emergence of programs in R&D policy represents the merger of two long-standing characteristics of the research system. First, *thematic priorities* were earlier found in the support for specialized research centers and institutes targeting specific technologies, industry sectors or policy areas. Second, *independent RFOs were established* in most countries in the first 5-6 decades of the 20th century, allocating funding through *competition* based on expert reviews.

3. Understanding R&D funding programs

Here we present some theoretical approaches that have been used to understand governmental R&D funding programs. The starting point is that understanding programs is related to the conceptualization of the relationship between government and science, since programs are policy means for steering the research performer toward the realization of specific public aims. This means that programs are tied to research funding organizations (RFOs) that play a major role in defining the characteristics of programs.

3.1 Theoretical approaches on governmental R&D programs

One stream of literature conceptualizes the relationship between government and science as a principal-agent game or relationship (Guston, 1996). Government acts as the principal, which hands over resources, often in a contractual relationship, to agents, the research performers, for the purpose of reaching certain goals that the principal cannot reach on its own. Van der Meulen (1998) and other colleagues (Braun, 1993; Id, 2017) elaborate on the characteristics of this relationship in R&D policy. Central aspects are information asymmetry between the principal and the agents, moral hazard in the implementation of the research, and path dependency as factor affecting the tendency toward stabilization of the funding system. Principal-Agent theory as analytical tool in R&D policy has been elaborated not as a bilateral game between the government and the science, but as a multi-actor game involving not only several agents, but also different principals, at least as a trilateral relationship between the government and the science but intermediate by the RFOs (Klerkx and Leeuwis, 2008).

Following principal-agent theory, R&D funding programs ensure that agents (the research performers) engage with the principals' (the RFOs) goals and priorities. Programs are designed by RFOs acting as principals on the base of a specific delegation from the government, which puts them in the position of intermediaries between the principal and the agents (van der Meulen, 2003; Kivisto & Mathies, in this book). However, programs require the involvement of research agents that are willing to participate, and their contributions need to fulfil certain quality criteria while addressing the principals' goals. It means that the steering capability of the programs under principal-agent theory is circumscribed by a) the existence of some research expertise to achieve the given aim; b) the willingness of agents to engage in the program; c) the ability of the principal to select the most appropriate agent for the work, and d) the ability of the principal to monitor and follow up funding. It has been found that "researchers' willingness to respond to top-down programming initiatives depends, to some extent, on the relation between that program and their own ambitions, their relative hunger for means of support, their chances of getting funding from other sources, and so forth." (Shove, 2003: 376).

Another approach is to consider programs as government policy instruments. Lascoumes and Le Galès (2007) depict the instruments as institutions that enable a policy to be operative and that organize the relationship between the public power and the recipients, according to the representations (goals) and meanings (values) that they incorporate. Thus, the instruments reveal (indicate) the real choices of public policies and their characteristics. This means that instruments incorporate a theory of the relationship between government and governed institutions, and that they are not neutral: they keep memory of the policies that created them, and they are vehicles of specific values. Using this theoretical perspective to conceptualize R&D programs has some implications:

- Programs can generate effects that are not connected to the original goals for which they were designed; these unintended effects can modify the goals and eventually distort them, creating stable ideas.
- As institutions, programs tend to persist through time, and they usually change incrementally by adding or changing specific devices rather than by radical breakthroughs. Because of the persistence through time, and the implementation inertia, RFOs generally use already existing programs, adapting them to the new policies, while only in rare cases removing or substituting the whole scheme (Hood, 1986).
- Changes in programs do not necessarily imply changing the policy goals. However, programs can be modified or substituted by others judged to be more effective, but modifications in the instruments themselves can modify the goals as well. In both cases, changes compel the actors to adapt; in this sense programs may be vectors of change and stability at the same time.

This highlights the problem of how policies balance elements of continuity and change (Pierson, 1993). Some authors have used concepts from policy feedback theory to understand how the institutionalization of some programs creates ideas informing other policies (e.g., the positive effects of broadening competition for funding, Wang et al., 2018) as well as values and beliefs that stabilize a given problem in the policy frame (e.g., the legitimate interest to shift R&D programs to goals addressing societal grand challenges).

A crucial element in the analysis of programs as policy instruments is the comprehension of the autonomy that they leave to the actors – how the instrument changes the actors’ policy spaces (Braun, 2006a). For instance, shaping objectives about performance (efficiency of the management and effectiveness of the results) can be implemented through compulsory rules, standards, or guidelines. In all the cases, the recipients have different room to maneuver and possibility to create spaces for action. Moreover, it is important to consider path dependency effects (North, 2000) that influence the present functioning of the programs and how they will affect future choices as well. Finally, it is worth to recall the role that ideas play in the design and implementation of policy instruments – and programs thereof, reducing the complexity of what is ought to be achieved through the instrument itself (Capano in this Handbook).

In sum, under this perspective, programs are instruments of governmental R&D funding policy, located at the meso level between politics and research performers (Reale and Seeber, 2013). Programs can be articulated as one single instrument or as a combination (or mix) of different instruments, involving aspects such as regulation, communication, and expert groups that aim to steer research (Flanagan et al., 2011; Kern et al., 2019) to achieve intended policy goals (Martin, 2016). Programs can also combine different organizational logics in their design, for example logics of hierarchical governance with logics of steering at the distance (Capano, 2019). Finally, R&D programs can in principle be characterized along the different typologies of the policy instruments (Vedung, 2007; Howlett, 2005; Martin, 2016; Peters, 2005). The use of typologies has not been fully exploited in the literature, although there are some recent works trying to explore this possibility (Capano, 2020; Lepori and Reale, 2019). Finally, it is worth to mention that the two theoretical approaches presented in the section, correspond to different (complementary) facets of the same process. Principal-agent theory is in fact one of the possible action mechanisms of public policies and programs are instruments of public policy largely working through delegation, which is indeed at the core of new public governance (Salamon, 2002).

3.2 The organizational dimension

We have seen that diversity is a structural feature of governmental R&D programs. The ‘program’ concept is fluid and non-homogeneous, given the multiplicity of actors involved with different objectives, logics, preferences, and the government levels where they are formulated, and effects are deployed. Even the wording – programs – can differ between countries, because of variations in sectors, funding context, and policy history.

The diversity characterizing R&D programs strongly depends on the organizational characteristics and policy space of RFOs managing them (Braun, 1998; Potì and Reale, 2007). Programs are complex objects that coordinate existing and emerging ideas about policy (knowledge and expectations about causality, Capano in this Handbook) and norms (preferences on how policy should be enacted on the base of past experiences, policy legacies and administrative traditions, cf. Hood, 1986 and Verhoest et al., 2009). RFOs are key policy actors designing, administering, and managing programs according to their own mission, objectives, strategies, and traditions of research funding. Programs may be funded from a combination of different policy areas and related ministries, which gives the RFOs a role in setting up new and combined goals (Braun, 1998). The Austrian Climate and Energy Fund funding energy-related research projects is an example that can be put in context in that respect.¹

In the P-A theory, RFOs have been conceptualized as mediators between the government and the research performers, and their policy spaces are shaped by the proximity between the policy level and the science community (Braun, 2006b). The intermediary approach focuses the interest on the capability of the RFOs to solve the tensions between the state and the research community (Braun, 2003) when R&D programs are concerned. For instance, Gulbrandsen (2005) pointed out the presence of six main tensions for the research councils, affecting the setting up of strategies, the procedures, and the organization of the science system and R&D programs thereof, creating problems of balancing between different options in research funding

¹ <https://www.bmk.gv.at/en/topics/climate-environment/climate-protection/climate-energy-fund.html>, last access 9 March 2022

(basic vs applied research; steering vs aggregation; disciplinary vs cross disciplinary; researchers vs users or stakeholders; reviewing vs monitoring). RFOs therefore can be characterized based on their position vis-a-vis the state (e.g., their capacity of autonomous decision-making), and the intermediary role they play between governors and the research community (van den Meulen, 2003), the functions they fulfil in the public research funding, and the influence they might have in the cognitive development of science (Braun, 1998). It is important to recall that RFOs shape the procedural and organizational dimensions in the program delivery package (Howlett, 2019), for instance by designing the selection procedures of the beneficiaries and the goal of the program, which allow to understand the underlining logics or policy frames of the instrument.

In sum, RFOs are important actors for shaping horizontal or vertical specialization of the national research funding system (Lepori, 2011) and the degree of control from the government. RFOs need to find an effective balance between different options in research funding programs: basic vs applied research, steering of the system toward achieving pre-determined objectives vs aggregation for a socially constructed research agenda, disciplinary vs cross disciplinary research, authority distribution between researchers and users/stakeholders, and types of reviewing and monitoring.

3.3 The main dimensions of R&D programs

Following Nedeva (2012), programs can be tied to two central dimensions. The first one is organizational because programs are found at the intersection of the international arena of the research field in question and the local research space shaped by the actors and unique context of a particular country, region or sector. This interaction leads to different considerations about what ‘good research’ may mean for a specific program, which will be based on combinations of criteria derived from research fields and societal sectors or spaces. Langfeld and colleagues (2019) name this a balance between F-type (research fields) and S-type (societal spaces) criteria. Programs can therefore be seen as instruments to manage tensions between these two sources of expectations to research.

The second dimension important to understand programs is their *scope*, which can be – depending on the orientation of the program itself between science fields and societal objectives – broader or narrower. The scope of the programs identifies relevant participants (in terms of research organizations and groups addressed), their main activities within the R&D spectrum, and their governance and related fundamental decision-making. For example, a program can be defined by a ministry in its allocation to a RFO, or it can be defined by the funding organization itself, and there may also be other actors participating in the design and implementation of the program.

We propose in Table 1 some stylized characteristics of programs based on their scope and organizational emphasis, relating in 2-by-2 matrix these two dimensions to differing thematic goals, research goals, and research-performing organizations objectives. In this way, the conceptualization of programs as means to coordinate ideas and norms can be operationalized through descriptors to empirically classify and study R&D programs. For instance, such a classification may be used as heuristic to investigate the portfolios of RFOs or to analyze changes in instruments over time. Also, this classification can be used to study the characteristic of the RFOs themselves on the base of the choices they made in programs design and implementation, and to highlight instances of hybridization in the public funding systems (see Section 3.4).

Table 1. Central characteristics of governmental R&D programs

Some characteristics of programs		Scope	
		Broad	Narrow
Organizational emphasis	Science fields (F-type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Programs that target an established scientific fields or discipline (physics, biomedicine etc.). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Programs that target an emerging area with scientific promise.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities will mainly be basic research. • Main participants will be found in academia and some research institutes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities: Basic and applied research, education/capacity building. • Participants: Academia, research institutes, some firms
	Society (S-type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programs that target wide areas like oceans, food, energy, maybe with reference to the UN sustainability development goals and similar. • Activities: Basic and applied research. • Participants: Most research organizations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programs that target specific societal problems. • Activities: Whole R&D spectrum including innovation • Participants: Applied research organizations, firms, hospitals, public actors

Source: Authors' own elaboration

The classification has limitations not least because the fields/societal space distinction can be unclear in many cases, and because the terms used to describe activities can be heterogeneous or contested. This raises challenges for the empirical observation of R&D programs, but empirical insights are needed, not only for underlining and potentially adapting the conceptualization of programs, but also in a policy evaluation context. In this context, we do observe an increasing interest in improving the empirical foundations for understanding instruments for governmental R&D and their diversity. For instance, the STIP Compass (OECD 2021) collects data based on a comprehensive survey, intended to characterize different policy instruments, including R&D programs, in particular in terms of the policy issues that are addressed, such as public research, business or service innovation, knowledge transfer (e.g., science-industry programs), but also issues like societal challenges and governance modes². Fig.1 provides an illustrative example visualization of R&D policy instruments implemented by the EU member states (current instruments, status 2019). It underlines the heterogeneous and diverse character of R&D programs and underlying instruments, indicating the frequency of instruments assigned to different classes (darker shades imply higher numbers of instruments in the specific category), as well as different budget ranges associated with each instrument. It can be seen that R&D funding related to grants for business R&D and innovation and project grants for public research are the most frequent R&D policy instruments used by the EU member states in the highest budget range (more than 500Mio EUR). Not only this simple example, but also related literature using STIP data (see, e.g. Borowiecki and Paunov 2018) underline the increasingly diverse composition of institutions and mechanisms of policy initiatives and related instruments.

Fig 1. R&D policy instruments used by the EU member states (STIP compass2019)

² The compass currently covers more than 7000 policy instruments, initiated across 50+ countries over the past 4 decades, with the instruments being attributed to five main categories according to their main function (governance, direct financial support, indirect financial support, collaborative infrastructures, guidance, and regulation), and more detailed 28 subcategories (EC-OECD, 2020). Its relevance has been underlined by the production of cross-country comparisons of national R&D policy programs (Borowiecki and Paunov 2018, Guimon and Paunov 2019, Capano et al., 2020). Other recent initiatives have tried to shift emphasis from survey-based to a more statistically and quantitative driven collection of data on R&D policy programs – directly collected from national statistical offices or even RFOs – to enable more meaningful cross-country comparisons or indicators production. Moreover, data science and semantic technologies inspired approaches are increasingly considered in the collection or the classification of programs in terms of their thematic orientations (e.g., societal challenges, Sustainable Development Goals).

Source: EC-OECD (2020), STIP Compass International Database on STI Policies, <https://stip.oecd.org>

The illustration put forward in Fig.1 at the same time underlines the difficulties and challenges for the systematic collection of data on R&D programs, related to conceptual ambiguities, but also data collection challenges and the classification of collected data programs in terms of their characteristics. Therefore, next to STIP, other research efforts are still in progress. For instance, recent endeavors tried to get a more systematic empirical overview on instruments from a systemic perspective, e.g., by collecting evidence on rationales, legitimation, and orientation of R&D funding. One example is the PREF study on national public research funding (Reale, 2017; Lepori et al., 2018; Primeri et al., 2014; Zacharewicz et al., 2019) has put strong emphasis on the identification of funding themes, fields, and the types of allocation (in particular competitive project-based R&D programs versus institutional funding), comparing countries in terms of their funding focus on societal challenges between 2008 and 2014. New initiatives currently under development³, try to deepen empirical foundations in that direction, experimenting with the usage of text mining methods to characterize R&D funding instruments more systematically, e.g., in terms of their relevance for Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

3.4 Changing configurations of programs coordination mixes and portfolio

We have seen that the increased fragmentation of policy landscapes of R&D funding with multiple goals, strategies, and agencies has been highlighted as a source of scarce coordination, weakening the steering capability of programs as incentives for pushing researchers toward a given goal, such as efficiently address

³ One example is the European dataset of public R&D funding instruments (EFIL) that is currently under development as one main part of the RISIS infrastructure for Science and Innovation Policy Studies (risis2.eu).

societal challenges (Larrue et al., 2018). The literature points out some theoretical knowledge gaps as to coordination of funding programs, and new directions of analysis to deepening the structure of policy mixes, the type of hybridity affecting the program design, and the possibility to adopt a portfolio approach.

Policy mixes refer to the interactions between instruments in different areas. Mixes might evolve over time in ways that may deviate from original goals, like the process for individual instruments described in the previous section. Also, a large variation in the way in which a given RFO combines different instruments at work is visible between and within countries, between and within RFOs (Braun, 2006a). Mixes related to programs of different research field, and it still remains a problematic issue under which conditions one instrument (or combination of instruments) can be more effective than another, and the feedback effects of one instrument on the others. Flanagan et al. (2011) proposed a conceptualization for policy mixes looking at dimensions in which the interactions between instruments can occur: across policy spaces, governance spaces, geographical spaces and time, and interactions between different instruments and across different dimensions of the same instruments. Tensions between instruments can rise from conflicts between policy rationales and goals, and from implementation approaches, thus setting conditions for success or failure of a given R&D funding policy (Kern et al. 2019; Edmondson et al, 2019).

A different focus is on the evolving *hybridity in the formulation of funding programs*, which is investigated as combination of different logics inside one program or as managing programs following different logics. Capano and Pritoni (2019) outline that policy instruments like R&D programs incorporate and combine in various way the traditional principles of coordination – hierarchy, market, and networks. In this context, hybridity can occur through compromising, which means incorporating elements of conflicting logics within the same program. In R&D funding program design, hybridity might affect the organizational logics by mixing features related to both fields and society goals, and the allocation criteria and target group addressed. The literature (Polzer et al., 2016) distinguishes between two ways of compromising, namely blending and layering. The former means generating new practices in which the original logics are joined together and cannot be separated; blending of funding programs might come from designing instruments by combining different allocation criteria, such as policy relevance and academic quality. Layering is the juxtaposition of elements introduced on top of pre-existing ones over time (Capano and Pritoni, 2019). For R&D funding programs this might be the presence within the same instrument of one competitive and one non-competitive component. A second type of hybridization is compartmentalization, where different logics coexist (Schelker and Smith, 2015). The authors distinguish between segmentation meaning the creation of programs enacting different logics within a single RFO, and segregation where programs are created by funding agencies enacting different logics and governance modes. Compartmentalization avoids conflicts between logics, but at the same time can generate coordinating issues between potentially inconsistent instruments (Braun, 2008). We can find several examples of programs promoted by research councils of European countries that fit to the mentioned characteristics, namely R&D funding schemes with very different logics and high coordination efforts (Reale et al., 2021).

Hybridity in R&D funding programs is still largely unexplored (Gulbrandsen, 2011; Gulbrandsen et al., 2015). Capano and Pritoni (2019) identify three ideal modes of hybrid systemic governance of higher education in Europe, namely performance-based, re-regulated, and goal oriented. Lepori et al. (2014) demonstrate that national programs aimed at funding transnational research blended three ideal type logics – integration, cooperation, and collaboration – allowing the design of programs fitting the interests of the actors involved like funding agencies, national or supranational actors. Other efforts are under development to understand how hybridity is concretely implemented in the funding program formulation, and how hybridization produce combination of different logics within the same program or setting new programs. In this respect one major gap is about understanding the effects – positive or negative – different types of hybridity can produce, and to explain how policy strategies are put into action by programs following complex mixes of incoherent ideas and values. Thus, a relevant research question can be: does hybrid funding program work? Does it work better than other types of funding that are not hybrid in nature?

Finally, it is worth to recall a third approach to study the coordination of R&D programs, which assume programs are in some settings increasingly put into a sort of *portfolio perspective* (Bozeman and Rogers, 2001) “in order to fulfil a widening set of objectives, from scientific excellence and economic relevance to contributing to a variety of societal challenges (inclusiveness, gender diversity, sustainability, etc.)” (Larrue et al., 2018). One may think of a program as a portfolio in itself (of projects) or sets of programs as a portfolio to address a scientific and/or societal need, whose management is characterized by the maximization of the value with respect to the intended achievements, the balance between different programs at stake, the coherence with the strategic goals and the capability to maintain alive the right number of programs with respect to the available resources. A portfolio perspective or governance is to reduce risk and uncertainties, but it may also be seen as a mean to increase the chances of radical originality/innovation or as a mean of coordination (Wallace et al., 2015). Despite the different focus of the analysis, there is a link between a portfolio perspective and the policy mix perspective in the sense that both highlight the evolutionary and complex nature of interplays between many actors and entities.

In this section we have aimed for a comprehensive overview of central theoretical frameworks that have been or can be used for better understanding R&D programs. Some frameworks derive from theories about the relationship between science and society, others take RFOs or the programs and funding instruments themselves as the starting point, or the relationship between instruments in a wider policy or funding context. Theoretical frameworks have emerged in tandem with new trends in R&D funding, highlighting the need also for studying programs from a longer-term and longitudinal perspective. Lastly, an interesting approach is to study funding programs by looking at configurations, trials, and amalgamations as suggested by Thomas and colleagues in this Handbook.

Concluding remarks

Governmental R&D funding programs have been under ongoing transformation over the past decades, both in terms of organizational emphasis and scope. This chapter has shed some light – from a theoretical and conceptual perspective – on the changing natures of programs as instruments of governmental R&D policy. It has sought to provide a comprehensive discussion and illustration of the increasing diversity and complexity of such programs, including multi-faceted strategies followed by an increasingly diverse set of engaging actors, in particular research funding organizations.

Moreover, it has connected these theoretical considerations with a discussion on recently established and currently developing efforts to get a richer and more systematic empirical picture on R&D funding programs coordination that is able to grasp and understand this increasing diversity and complexity, and to empirically relate program characteristics to, for instance, outcomes on the performance side in a more robust way, taking into account the outcomes are not just dependent on programs characteristics or funding volume, but also on many other factors.

Still, we have shown that empirical research has sought to grasp program characteristics and manifold orientations more systematically, especially in the past decade, e.g. the STIP monitor or the currently developed EFIL database within the RISIS infrastructure. Clearly, these initiatives are still experimental but will provide important insights into the potentials, and the barriers to systematic data collection activities on governmental R&D programs. In this context, precisely evaluating the advantages and the pitfalls – also based on illustrative use cases – will be essential to derive conclusions for future data collection activities.

Some gaps emerge in the study of government public R&D funding. One concerns the ideational dimension of governmental R&D programs and how they are put into action. On the one hand, the distance between the original goal and aim of the policy makers and the actual formulation of the instruments by the RFO has been not sufficiently empirically documented, with a limited capability to understand factors affecting the translation process of policy rationale in the instruments. On the other hand, the evidence about how the opportunities provided by the funding programs have been understood by the performers and then

translated in research projects, is still limited. Therefore, the capability of governmental funding programs to steer public research remains largely unknown.

Limitations also are visible in the investigation of the selection and evaluation process of R&D proposal eligible for funding under a given program. The characterization of the funding programs as to the objectives, conditions for eligibility, and evaluation criteria, could be extremely useful to compare patterns of changes of R&D strategies in different countries shedding light on actual implementation of the programs. Proposals are evaluated separately, but empirical investigations could benefit from analysis of whole programs or even sets of programs.

Several developments can be outlined for R&D funding programs, which might be a source of new research avenues. First, the recent emphasis on mission-oriented policies to address Grand Challenges and Sustainable Development Goals (see Section 2), can result in a stronger and more pervasive focus and control toward the achievement of policy goals. This development might be further reinforced by the new awareness about the social responsibility of the scholars' community and the need to produce an impact, thus contributing to solve societal problems. Does it result increasing strategic and organizational diversity of R&D funding programs? Second, we can envisage a strong influence from the Covid-19 pandemic on R&D funding programs, which will be a crucial research focus in the coming years, including learning from widespread pandemic-oriented R&D programs that were set up quickly in 2020. It is not clear whether this may induce pendulum swings between the different scopes and logics described in this chapter. Third, there is a large potential with new data to contribute to the discussion on effects of R&D funding mechanisms on research performance and impact, even if impact fundamentally rests on characteristics beyond the funding program itself. As such, studies of impact may put R&D programs in a wider science-society setting, which can be a source of fruitful new research questions that can be addressed through new data available and their combinations.

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